

EXAMINING THE PROFESSIONALISM OF EFL TEACHERS: WHY DOES THIS TOPIC REMAIN RELEVANT?

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Abstract

This research aims to find out a broad picture of EFL teacher professionalism. This research explains the characteristics possessed by Professional EFL English teachers. In the review presented in this article, the literature study focuses on research published in many reputable national and international journals following the professional studies of EFL teachers. The results of the study show that the aspects reflected by professional EFL teachers are knowledge about students, knowledge about the subject matter, knowledge about teaching strategies, factors that influence teacher professionalism, and professional development. The professionalism of an EFL English teacher is related to the teacher's views or beliefs regarding how professional aspects are acquired and developed.

Keywords: Professionalism, EFL Teacher, Literature Study.

INTRODUCTION

Professional teachers have become essential in education because successful teaching requires experienced teachers. Therefore, professional educators determine the success of their education. Professional teachers impact student achievement the most (Canales & Maldonado, 2018). Several studies on professional characteristics and teachers have been conducted by (Lunenberget al., 2014; Leong & Ahmadi, 2017; Handayani, 2017; Al-Seghayer, 2017; Watt, Richardson, & Morris, 2017; Luo & Garner, 2017; Ping et al., 2018, Wyatt, 2018; Yashima, MacIntyre, & Ikeda, 2018; Guan, Song & Li, 2018; Tania, & Maru, 2018; Külekçi, 2018; Klassen, Durksen, Al Hashmi, Kim, Longden, Metsäpelto, & Györi, 2018; Kiatkheeree, 2018; Van Velzen et al., 2019 2020; Saiful, 2020; Taie, & Goldring, 2020; Hobson & Maxwell, 2020; Cenoz & Gorter, 2020; Darmawan, Wahyudin, & Ali, 2020; Korkmazgil, & Seferoğlu, 2021).

Leong & Ahmadi (2017); Yashima, MacIntyre, & Ikeda (2018); Tania & Maru (2018); Keller, Vögelin, Jansen, Machts, & Möller (2019); Gralowski (2019); Francisco (2020); Saiful, (2020); Darmawan, Wahyudin, & Ali (2020); Korkmazgil, & Seferoğlu (2021) found that professional teachers are teachers who have competent knowledge and skills. Handayani (2017), Luo & Garner (2017), Guan, Song & Li (2018), and Kiatkheeree (2018) revealed that professional teachers are reflected in their competency skills in practical learning reflected in their ability to manage learning situations. Al-Seghayer (2017); Külekçi (2018); Dewaele, Magdalena, & Saito (2019); van der Kleij (2019); Taie & Goldring (2020) found that professional teachers are teachers who can display attitudes and abilities that are reflected in the teacher's character in the classroom. Watt, Richardson, & Morris (2017) found that professional teachers have good knowledge competencies reflected in understanding the material and science in the school.

Wyatt (2018) found that professional teachers are teachers with scientific abilities reflected in their skills and academic background. Klassen, Durksen, Al Hashmi, Kim, Longden, Metsäpelto, & Györi (2018) found that professional teachers have good knowledge, attitudes, and skills in teaching. Cenoz & Gorter (2020) found that professional teachers have pedagogical competence.

The initial assumption in this research is what professional characteristics EFL teachers have. Based on the explanation above, this topic is significant because it can look at the professional aspects of teachers, especially EFL teachers. Based on the initial assumptions of this research and from initial observations in the field, personal and social competency skills dominate the characteristics of English teachers' professionalism from teachers such as pedagogy and professionalism based on literature studies. Based on the background explanation above, the importance of researching or revealing how professional EFL teachers are is an exciting thing to discuss. Based on previous research, research does not fully explain the characteristics of qualified EFL teachers in its explanations. In other words, previous research still leaves unresolved problems, so a study on teacher professional development and the characteristics of professional EFL teachers must be carried out to reveal more valuable findings after considering the justification above.

Based on the background of the problem, the following issues can be identified: What are the characteristics of a professional EFL English teacher? Based on the research topic, the author proposed several limitations in conducting this research, as follows: According to the recommended research specifications, the subject of this research is limited to the professional aspect of teachers in the form of teacher competence. Based on the background of the problem that has been stated, the goal to be achieved is to explain the patterns, characteristics, and factors that influence the professional aspects of EFL English teachers.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method uses qualitative research, a type of literature research from Creswell & Creswell (2017). Literature study is research concerned with collecting library data, reading and taking notes, and processing research material to produce overall conclusions. Sampling was conducted using a purposive sample (Creswell & Creswell, 2017), considering several journal characteristics, such as Google Scholar and Scopus journals. The data source for this research was taken from thirty-three international research journals. This data collection aims to obtain a good literature study on the journal's reputation, used as a reference in data collection. The analytical approach in this research uses exploratory, inductive steps. Next, an in-depth discussion is carried out in the related literature or reviewed section.

RESULTS

Research on teacher professionalism comes from Lunenberg et al. 2014 Ping et al. 2018; Van Velzen et al., 2019; Hobson & Maxwell, 2020. Lunenberg et al. (2014) found that professional development focused on teacher education. In this case, teacher education is the role of teacher education in developing teacher professionalism to become teaching staff. Lunenberg found

that there was little professional teacher development that focused on teachers becoming researchers or trainers. Lunenberg et al. (2014) stated that professional development focuses on teacher learning to produce professional aspects that teachers carry out in the classroom.

Ping et al. (2018) found that teacher professional development focuses on abilities and their acquisition from teachers or educators. Ping et al. concluded that teacher education, research, and scholarship are oriented toward competent practice. Ping et al. (2018) explain that the reflection and collaboration actions that have been carried out constitute internal professional development.

Czerniawski et al. (2017) concluded that fostering learning needs for teachers or educators is essential. This research explains that teacher professional development is passive (for example, not making teaching innovations or acquiring knowledge, so teachers are not productive). Another study of teacher professional development demonstrated the importance of formal and informal training (McNamara et al., 2014). McNamara said casual and formal learning is critical in the workplace or institutions where teachers teach because it can develop professional and personal attitudes. It also involves learning experiences on the job.

Cochran-Smith et al. (2019) found that examples of teacher professional development are independent study and conducting research. Cochran-Smith et al. (2019) revealed that teacher or educator development can be done through independent study, research, and training at the start of a career as a teacher. Murray (2016) states that teacher professional development can take the form of teacher education. In the Anglophone context, teacher professional development is related to diversity, homogeneity, and multiethnicity plays an essential role in development (Yuan, 2017; Lampert & Burnett, 2016; Ellis & Maguire, 2017)

According to Canales and Maldonado (2018), teacher competency in the learning process is a factor that influences student learning achievement. To promote quality education, teachers who do not have the necessary qualifications are a significant problem (Cochran-Smith et al., 2020). According to Cochran-Smith et al., (2020), only a tiny percentage of teachers in education meet teaching and intellectual capabilities.

Principles or actions taken to guide decision-making are called policies. The policy relates to intellectual tasks in making decisions and citing, including outlining goals, outlining trends, analyzing circumstances, projecting future development and research, assessment and research, and evaluating and selecting possibilities (Moh Abdul Fattah, 2023). Policies regarding teacher professionalism relate to the development of human resources themselves. The human resource component (educators/educational personnel) is the most crucial and critical component in achieving the goal of superior education. The problem is, what human resource components can be utilized to attain educational effectiveness and efficiency through professionalism development programs?

Teacher competency, especially English teacher competency, cannot be separated from the characteristics of teacher growth. Teacher training, curriculum training based on institutional features, and development based on individual ability or professional competence are examples of progress (Richard and Ferrell, 2005). Based on the explanation, teacher professionalism, such

as attitudes, values, sentiments, motivation, and habits, are crucial to professional development and competence (Sulistiyo, 2016). English teachers in West Java must know about the learning process to play an essential role in teaching and learning activities. Thus, teacher competence becomes an integral aspect of the subjects students study in every learning process.

Teacher competency is considered a professional factor determining student learning success (Wardoyo & Firmansyah, 2020). Concerning the relevance of professional competence, increasing teacher professionalism must be prioritized. It raises crucial considerations, such as factors influencing teachers' professional competence in the classroom. According to Kartal and Basol (2019), good teachers have professional competence and a good personality. Alzeebeere and Zebari (2021) state that good teachers are knowledgeable, intellectual, and caring. Wirantaka and Wahyudianawati (2021) found that good teachers have a positive personal attitude and the capacity to communicate material.

Based on the description above, the growth of English teachers cannot be separated from the teaching profession in terms of teaching competency. Competence as a facilitator is one of their professional attributes. Professional teachers can guide students through the learning process at school. Teachers' professional aspects in the learning process include the ability to prepare effective learning plans, master learning principles, select and use learning media, select and use teaching methods, select and use learning strategies or approaches, and assess student learning outcomes.

Facilities and teacher competence indicate the quality of teaching at school. The problem is that English in the classroom is still inadequate (Khanum & Siddiqui, 2018; Sarwanti, 2019). School facilities and teacher competency, especially in Rural areas, have worse access to junior high school education than in urban areas (Holgún & Morales, 2016). As a result, most rural areas still have inadequate schools and teachers. Regarding competency, teachers in rural areas must have English language competency in junior high schools, which is related to the curriculum used. In the curriculum, English language learning in middle school is targeted so that students can reach a functional level, namely functioning well through oral and written communication to solve everyday problems (Siswandi, 2018). Thus, teachers are required to have English language competence to determine the essential themes that students must master at this level.

The English subject curriculum at the junior high school level aims to develop the ability (competence) to communicate in English (Inayah, Komariah, & Nasir, 2019). These communication skills include reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills. Apart from that, mastery of the elements of English is needed to support the ability to communicate orally and in writing. These four abilities will make it easier for someone to respond or create discourse in international life and relationships. Therefore, English subject teachers are required to have communicative competence so that suitable learning activities can be designed.

In practice, the language teaching curriculum can allow students to participate actively in learning. This curriculum is student-centered and develops student character to suit their competencies. According to Nadhiroh & Anshori (2023), in an independent learning

curriculum, learning plans made by teachers must be presented so that students do not feel pressured to learn. The problem is that teachers must be able to guide and direct them. Based on this explanation, the issues in the Merdeka curriculum related to aspects of teacher professionalism are how teachers can implement the independent learning curriculum and improve critical thinking skills in learning.

The teaching profession cannot be separated from the basic concepts of other professions. The term profession is a broad concept that involves many aspects (Evans, L. (2011), Tarman (2012); Huang (2013); Evetts (2013); Carr, D. (2014); Cauvin, T., & O'Neill, C. (2017); Révai, N., & Guerriero, S. (2017); Fraser-Arnott, M. A. (2019) Healy, L. M., & Thomas, R. L. (2020)).

Evans, L. (2011) explains that the term profession is related to practices or actions at work. Perceptions of professions relate to specific tasks and skills. In other words, the concept of profession includes work that requires expertise, professional which refers to the performance of someone who carries out the work. The idea of the teaching profession was mentioned by Tarman (2012). Tarman said that the teaching profession is related to a positive attitude towards the profession, behavior, and commitment. It explains that the teacher's performance in teaching is associated with the teacher's positive attitude.

Another concept of a profession is explained by Huang (2013). Huang mentioned that the profession, primarily the academic profession, refers to all people who teach or conduct research or produce publications based on scientific research at universities or research institutions inside or outside colleges or universities. In a narrower sense, the academic profession is defined as any faculty member, including a professor, associate professor, lecturer, or assistant professor, primarily involved with teaching and research activities in higher education.

Evetts (2013) mentions several characteristics of the profession. According to Evetts, there is a difference between profession and job. The difference is a difference of degree rather than kind. For Evetts, profession and work talk not only about how to solve a problem but also about the way of thinking of a profession. Concerning teaching as a profession, Carr (2014) argues that the concepts of the profession, professionalism, and professional behavior are behavior and work that follows applicable rules (based on government standards). According to Carr, profession or professionalism is often associated with improving work standards.

Chakraborty and Mondal (2014) explained that teaching is closely related to professional and positive attitudes. According to Chakraborty and Mondal, the teacher's commitment to maintaining attitude and professionalism is essential in the learning process. Zhu and Li (2019) state that teaching is a profession. Zhu and Li explore the teaching profession holistically from transformative, communicative, and instructional views. The teaching profession is said to have a transformative perspective involving changes in teacher awareness; the communicative aspect consists of the teacher's communication skills, and the instructional part involves the teacher's way of teaching. It shows that the teaching profession is a profession that involves holistic processes.

In more detail, an explanation of aspects of the profession was put forward by Bransford et al. (2005) & Richards (2015). Bransford et al. revealed various aspects of teaching, including Knowledge about Students, Subject Matter, and Teaching Strategies). Teacher competency, especially English teacher competency, cannot be separated from the professional characteristics of the teacher himself. Teacher training, curriculum training based on institutional factors, and development based on individual ability or professional competence are examples of progress (Richard and Ferrell, 2005). Based on the explanation, developing attitudes, values, sentiments, motivation, and habits is crucial to professional and competency development (Sulistiyo, 2016). English teachers in West Java must know about the learning process to play an essential role in teaching and learning activities. Thus, teacher competence becomes an integral aspect of the subjects students study in every learning process.

Teacher competency is considered a professional factor determining student learning success (Wardoyo & Firmansyah, 2020). Regarding the relevance of professional competence, increasing teacher professionalism must be prioritized. It raises crucial considerations, such as factors influencing teachers' professional competence in the classroom. According to Kartal and Basol (2019), good teachers have professional competence and a good personality. Alzeebeere and Zebari (2021) state that good teachers are knowledgeable, intellectual, and caring. Wirantaka and Wahyudianawati (2021) found that good teachers have a positive personal attitude and the capacity to communicate material.

Based on this explanation, it can be concluded that the professional aspects of English teachers related to teacher competence in the learning process include four factors, namely: (1) Professional Competence, (2) Pedagogy, (3) Personality, and (4) Social. Professional competency is a teacher's ability to master content development and integrate teaching materials into teaching and learning activities (Nessipbayeva, 2012). Toom (2017) explains two types of professional competencies: propositional knowledge and procedural knowledge. Propositional knowledge is knowledge related to understanding a material or science, and procedural knowledge is an ability related to the procedure or application of a material or science. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that professional competence is related to mastery and how to use knowledge and teaching materials.

Pedagogical Competency, or teaching and pedagogical skills, is mastery of techniques, theories, and strategies in teaching (Liakopoulou, 2011). Pedagogical competence contributes to teacher effectiveness, which can help teaching practices in the classroom. Mirzagitova & Akhmetov (2015) explained that in pedagogical competence, there is self-control of pedagogical competence, namely self-assessment of pedagogical abilities, which include knowledge (theory), technique, innovation, and pedagogical management. In other words, pedagogical competence relates to how teachers master carrying out and assessing processes, knowledge (theory), and teaching procedures to make learning efficient and on target.

Personality competency is the ability of a teacher's personality attitudes related to a teacher's professional role in teaching (Liakopoulou, 2011). Personality competencies include teacher traits or personalities such as flexibility, appearance, sense of humor, justice, patience, enthusiasm, creativity, attention, and interest in the teacher's learning. In other words,

personality competence is the ability of the affective and behavioral aspects related to the teacher's nature and behavior.

Social competence is the teacher's ability to carry out social activities. A teacher must possess this ability to communicate and socialize. Social competence in this context relates to behaving objectively and not discriminating against students based on differences in gender, race, religion, physical condition, family background, and social status, being able to communicate effectively, firmly, and politely with fellow teachers (educators). Parents and society can adapt to various regions of Indonesia, which have social and cultural diversity, and they must also be able to communicate with the teacher community and other professions through written and oral communication or other forms of communication. These four competency categories are the aspects that play the most role in successful learning (Izadinia, 2015 & Owen, 2016). Thus, research on teacher professionals in rural areas is an important topic. Regarding the importance of professional teachers, the critical issues are the factors that arise in teachers' professional development.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the literature study, an explanation of the professional aspects of EFL teachers can be explained through various elements of teaching as a profession, including Knowledge about Students, Knowledge about Subject Matter, and Knowledge about Teaching Strategies, factors that influence teacher professionalism, and Professional Development.

Knowledge about Students

The importance of student knowledge for teachers is an aspect that has an essential role in the professional attitude of EFL teachers in schools. Various aspects of student knowledge can be considered crucial to a good learning process. One aspect of students that teachers must know is pedagogical development (Nind, Kilburn & Wiles, 2015). Students' socio-cultural knowledge is needed in the learning process. Socio-cultural knowledge has a role in bringing out critical aspects of students (Mavuru & Ramnarain, 2017)

Vocabulary knowledge can determine learning or academic achievement. Students' academic success can be achieved through vocabulary knowledge (Masrai & Milton, 2018). Knowledge of assessing (assessment) teachers' teaching methods is a factor possessed by students as a strategy in the learning process. Knowledge of students' learning strategies supports students' achievement and understanding of learning (Glogger-Frey, Ampatziadis, Ohst, & Renkl (2018) & Mustafa (2021).

Based on the explanation above, the aspects that teachers must know about their students is that students' knowledge can vary. Diversity of knowledge is the nature of students who are always different from each other. Their differences may include their culture, economic background, cognitive abilities, and motivation. Professional teachers must know how to handle culturally diverse students. Teachers must have broad teaching strategies for students with different cultural backgrounds.

Knowledge of the Subject Matter

The study's results show that knowledge of the subject matter impacts teachers' professional formation. Knowledge about teaching materials or materials in teaching involves knowledge in delivery, skills, and attitudes. Knowledge of Subject Matter Is the inclusion of knowledge about the teacher's subject matter in the teaching and learning process, which impacts teaching and learning Jadama (2014). A teacher's subject matter knowledge affects the teaching and learning process in school. The research results reveal that mastery of the material involves using authentic material and development programs for teachers. It is in line with the role of content or teaching materials as an essential component in learning (Berry, Depaepe, & Van Driel (2016) & Herold & Waring, (2017)

Teacher knowledge about subject matter is obtained through teacher training and development programs. Teacher knowledge about teaching material is critical because teachers have little mastery. The study results show that teachers' knowledge of subject matter and pedagogical content is the basis for the teacher's basic knowledge. Based on this, it can be said that teacher training and development are vital to improving teacher professionalism (Chan & Yun (2018), Smith & Sudweeks (2019), & Canh (2020)

Knowledge of Teaching Strategies

The study results show that various aspects of knowledge about the importance of teaching knowledge have a meaningful impact on teachers' professional formation. Increasing student learning motivation and teacher teaching motivation is a practical step in learning (Vibulpho, 2016). Other studies reveal that the use of Scaffolding and QARs (Question Answer Relationship) teaching methods as teaching strategies has a positive impact (Sarjan (2017). Using learning videos is an effective teaching strategy in the classroom (Dos Santos (2019).

Knowledge about teaching is related to the teacher's teaching strategy so that students can understand fully (Wibowo, Syafrizal, & Syafryadin, 2020). Determining teaching strategies through appropriate teaching media is a practical step in teaching vocabulary (Simamora & Oktaviani, 2020). Argue that asynchronous teaching strategies use alternative media to support the online learning process (Putri & Sari, 2021). With this, it is clear that a teacher needs to master various strategies so that learning can occur better and more effectively. Teachers can master these different teaching strategies through various teacher professional development programs.

Factors That Influence Professional Teachers

This section's results describe the aspects that influence teacher professionalism. In general, acquiring teachers' professional characteristics does not only come from one source. The discussion results propose six factors that play a role in teacher professionalism. These aspects include general knowledge skills, focused training, teaching experience, subject matter knowledge, certifications, and academic degrees.

Based on the study's results, one aspect that influences teaching success is the teacher's knowledgeability. General knowledgeability is the cognitive ability to acquire knowledge. It is a mental act or process of gaining knowledge through thinking, experience, and the Senses (Liu & Kleinsasser, 2015). This general cognitive ability shapes teacher professionalism (Krupchenko, A., Inozemtzeva, K., & Prilipko, E. (2015). A teacher with high cognitive skills can design learning activities that interest students. Learning activities, such as inspirational ones, will strengthen students' motivation.

Literature studies show that professional development is vital to teacher professionalism (Steele & Zhang, 2016; Astuti, Wardana, Puspawati, & Sukanadi, 2018). Steele & Zhang, (2016). Professional development involves learning to improve existing conditions. According to Astuti et al., professional development is part of the teacher-learning process and must be carried out continuously throughout life. Astuti, Wardana, Puspawati, & Sukanadi, (2018). Based on this, inexperienced teachers should receive more training because there is a difference in expertise between experienced and inexperienced teachers.

Teacher training is significant for inexperienced and novice teachers because they are often unprepared when teaching in the classroom (Mede & Işık, 2016). Studies show that teacher training has an essential impact on teacher competency. Teacher training consists of curriculum, material development, teaching techniques, and teaching evaluation (Shawer, 2017).

Another study revealed the role of professional development training in the success of classroom teaching (Bayar, 2014). Bayar said that training has a significant contribution to the development of teacher professionalism. In other words, the role of teacher training should focus on aspects such as subjects, academic content, and curriculum.

A study from Fitchett & Heafner (2018) revealed that experience is one of the contributions to forming teacher theories. Teacher experience relates to professionalism (training), classroom practice, and teaching reflection. It all becomes the teacher's cognitive information, which forms or forms the teacher's characteristics represented in daily teaching activities as his teaching career develops.

Teaching experience also shapes teacher quality (Churchward & Willis, 2019). The study shows that teacher experience is essential in developing teacher professionalism. As already mentioned, teacher experience is part of the aspects that shape teacher characteristics, and this, in turn, influences the formation of teachers' theories, which influence teachers' teaching practices in the classroom (It is a common practice that teachers learn from their daily activities to improve their teaching performance.

Other studies show that academic qualifications are an aspect of teacher professionalism (Wardoyo & Herdiani, 2017; Prasetyo, Ilham, & Asvio, 2022). The contribution of a teacher's academic degree primarily results from the conception of professional teaching standards set by the educational institution of teacher candidate study. The concept of professional teaching standards has been designed by policymakers, educators, and teacher educators. It includes universities and government agencies.

Teacher Professional Development

Study results show that teacher professionalism is closely related to professional development (Guskey, 2002; Avalos, 2011; Vanassche and Berry, 2019). Guskey's (2002) study shows that high-quality professional development is central to improving education. Avalos (2011) explains that teacher professionalism development is related to increasing teacher capabilities through professional development. Vanassche and Berry (2019) stated that teacher professional development is about developing teacher knowledge and practice for the benefit of students. Teachers' or educators' professional knowledge combines solid theoretical knowledge with practical skills, competence, and interpersonal communication experience (Vanassche et al., 2021). In other words, teacher professional development is related to the knowledge obtained and the practices that individual teachers have carried out to reflect their professional competence. Teacher professional development generally includes teaching practice, reflecting on teaching practice, views on values and teaching principles, and social and work relationships with other teacher colleagues.

CONCLUSION

I began this paper by asking why teacher professionalism is still a topic of discussion. Professional EFL English teachers generally refer to growing understanding and abilities about teaching and themselves (attitudes) as teachers. Thus, teacher professionalism is related to teachers' professional experience and skills. Teacher professionalism is related to education, knowledge about students, knowledge about the subject matter, and knowledge about teaching strategies, factors that influence teacher professionalism, and professional development that follows professional rules. These rules include knowledge about students, knowledge about subject matter, and knowledge about teaching strategies. In addition, English Teacher professionalism has six aspects: general knowledge abilities, focused training, teaching experience, subject matter knowledge, certification, and academic degrees.

General knowledgeability is the cognitive ability to obtain or acquire mental knowledge through thinking, experience, and the senses. Developing general knowledge abilities is vital in shaping teacher professionalism because they can design learning activities that arouse students' interest.

Professional development is vital in teacher professionalism, which involves learning to improve existing conditions. Teacher training is significant for teachers who are often unprepared when teaching in the classroom. Teacher training has many aspects, including curriculum, material development, teaching techniques, and teaching evaluation. Experience is an essential contribution to teachers' professional development. Teacher experience includes training, classroom practice, and teaching reflection. Teacher experience is one aspect that shapes teacher characteristics and influences the formation of the teacher's personality, which affects the teacher's teaching professionalism in the classroom. Academic qualifications are an aspect of teacher professionalism development, which includes a teacher's academic title, which an academic institution determines. Policymakers, educators, and teacher education, including universities and government agencies, create professional teaching related to

educational qualifications. EFL English teacher professionalism is related to professional development based on competency, teacher knowledge, and practice development. In other words, the professional development of English teachers is related to the competencies obtained, which are put into practice in the classroom. English teachers' professional development includes both individual and institutional perspectives. From a personal perspective, the professionalism of English teachers is related to several areas of professional competency development, such as subject matter knowledge, pedagogical expertise, self-awareness, understanding of students, understanding of curriculum and materials, and career advancement. The development of English teacher professionalism from an institutional perspective includes teacher training, such as institutional development of staff and teachers, career development, and increasing students' knowledge levels.

Furthermore, the professionalism of an English teacher is related to the teacher's views or beliefs regarding how professional aspects are acquired and developed. Teachers' views and beliefs regarding teacher professional development can be divided into four categories: technical knowledge, pedagogical skills, interpersonal skills, and personal qualities. In development, six aspects influence the professionalism of English teachers. The six aspects that play a role in developing teacher professionalism include general knowledge abilities, training, experience, subject matter knowledge, certification, and academic degrees.

The conclusion identifies the professional characteristics of EFL teachers. This topic is significant because it sheds light on the professional aspects of teachers, particularly those teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL). Literature studies suggest that personal and social competency skills, alongside pedagogy and professionalism, dominate the characteristics of EFL teachers' professionalism. Given this result, the professionalism of EFL teachers is crucial, and professional EFL teachers' attributes are necessary to uncover more valuable insights.

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